

Africa International Journal of Management Education and Governance
(AIJMEG) 1(2),43-58

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KNOWLEDGE IMPLEMENTATION AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE; EVIDENCE FROM
KENYA

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Received in 23rd June 2016

Received in Revised Form on 28th July 2016

Accepted on 8th August 2016

ABSTRACT

Purpose – The purpose of this paper was to examine the interaction effect of employee engagement on the relationship between knowledge implementation and employee performance in Technical Institutions in Kenya. The study therefore, sought to establish the relationship between knowledge implementation and employee performance and the moderating effect of employee engagement on the relationship between knowledge implementation and employee performance.

Methodology– The paper adopts regression model and Baron and Kenny approach to test for moderation effects.

Findings –The study findings revealed that there is a positive and significant relationship between knowledge implementation and employee performance ($\beta = .083, p < .05$). The study further revealed that employee engagement moderates the relationship between knowledge implementation and employee performance ($\beta = -.142, p < .01$).

Research Limitations/implications– Given that the study looked at knowledge implementation, employee engagement and employee performance at one point in time, longitudinal time span research is recommended to provide more insights on these variables. A longitudinal approach may also help in improving the models ability to make causal statements

Theoretical implications - The study contributes to theory by not only examining knowledge attributes but by analyzing empirically the extent of the relationship between knowledge implementation, employee engagement and employee performance.

Originality/value – This is the first study that focuses on testing the moderating effect of employee engagement on the relationship between knowledge implementation and employee performance in Technical Institutions in Kenya.

Key words- Knowledge implementation, employee engagement, employee performance

Introduction

Globally it is widely accepted that we are now in a period of shift from industrial society to information society and a transition from information society to knowledge society. Knowledge society recognizes the key role of information-based technologies in providing a basis for the generation, management and utilization of knowledge (Webb, 1998; Hansen, Nohria and Tierney, 1999; Earl, 2001; World Bank and European Training Foundation, 2005; Hussain, 2009; Oxtan; 2013). Among the first organizations to pay attention and embrace knowledge as a strategic resource were the consultancy firms, Health care providers, and

manufactures of computers in the United States of America. They made heavy investments in knowledge management practices and they reaped the benefits in terms of improved performance. These companies, depending on their business strategy, employee characteristics, top management leadership style and customer needs adopted knowledge implementation as a way of improving performance (Hansen *et al*, 1999; Donoghue *et al.*, 1999; Armstrong, 2006).

The success stories of companies that embraced knowledge management practices led to more organizations in Europe, Australia, and Asia and across the globe to follow suit. Africa was

not left behind. A World Bank report on Integrating Technical Vocation Education and Training (TVET) into the knowledge economy in Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region covered Egypt, Jordan, Lebanon and Tunisia and one of the recommendations of the report was to refocus the role of TVET as an instrument for the knowledge economy (World Bank and European Training Foundation, 2005). Mosoti and Masheka (2010) acknowledge that an electronic network in Africa has been created to foster connections across varying boundaries and to create a knowledge bank that links expertise with demand. Bahenyi (2007) pointed out that Knowledge Management Africa (KMA) has become a knowledge engine that drives appropriate development solutions for Africa. The mission of KMA is to promote the use of Africa's collective knowledge as a key development resource and establish knowledge management platforms that will create access to existing networks and facilitate the sharing and implementation of knowledge across all sectors. Knowledge Management Africa organizes biennial conferences in different countries to boost the implementation of Knowledge in Africa. Conferences have been held in different Africa countries to fine-tune this new management concept called knowledge and the second conference was held in Nairobi on July 2007 and it brought together diverse international development finance institutions, sector professionals and civil-society organizations and one of the key objectives was to explore a range of tools for research, communication, knowledge sharing, and building relationships among professionals with similar interests. This was aimed at facilitating knowledge sharing and implementation across different sectors. Information Africa Organization made a call for papers for 2015 conference and the theme of the conference is knowledge management and Innovation: Transforming Africa through Knowledge. This shows that Africa has embraced knowledge management as a key component in enhancing employee and organization performance. Mosoti and Masheka (2010) share the same view and observed that though some Kenyan organizations have embraced knowledge management practices, however, there is still a lot that needs to be done in relation to

knowledge creation, capture, sharing, retention, protection and implementation in order for organization to benefit from knowledge resources. Leadership, culture, organizational strategies and employee characteristics are factors highlighted by the study to hinder knowledge management practices and therefore, there is need to address them in moving Kenya forward (Bahenyi, 2007; Mosoti and Masheka, 2010). One dimension of employee characteristic that has been established to influence employee performance is employee engagement. Whereas theoretical assertions confirm that employee engagement influences performance (Khan, 1990; Gallup, 1995; Saks, 2005:2006; Vance, 2006; Hewitt, 2013) empirical evidence in the existing literature is limited and reveals mixed findings (Murphy 2013; Liaci and Juapi, 2014).

Whereas Kenya has become a middle income economy and working towards becoming a knowledge society by implementing the Vision 2030 (Ministry of Education Science and Technology, 2011) TVET has been identified as a key player in producing technical competencies. To become industrialized, Kenya requires the technical competencies from TVET institutions that match the requirements of the knowledge economy and this can be partly achieved through knowledge implementation and more so in engaging TVET employees in order for them to remain committed to the TVET institutions. This paper therefore in moving forward these concepts and building on previous studies, specifically links knowledge implementation, employee engagement and employee performance in TVET institutions in Kenya.

Statement of the Problem

From theoretical perspective, knowledge management as a conscious practice is still young (Hansen *et al.*, 1999). Donoghue *et al.*, (1999) agrees with Hansen *et al.*, (1999) and contend that knowledge management is still a relatively young but steadily growing field, with new concepts emerging constantly and thus need for more consensus to be built through research because more often, these new concepts are portrayed simplistically in form of discussions which typically revolve around blanket principles that are intended to work across the organizations. Therefore there is need

for empirical evidence.

Resource based view has been criticized on various issues. Fahy (2000) noted that the vast majority of contributions within the resource based view have been conceptual in nature rather than empirical. This implies that most of its fundamental tenets still remain to be validated in the field and the most notable were the debates between Barney, (2001a) and Priem and Butler (2001a, 2001b) on the relevancy and validity of the resource-based view. This study therefore, investigated the empirical role of employee engagement on the relationship between knowledge implementation and employee performance.

Extant literature revealed that researchers have focused on various aspects of knowledge management for instance, knowledge classification (Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995), knowledge management strategies (Hansen *et al.*, 1999; Donoghue *et al.*, 1999), tacit knowledge (Dreoge and Hobbler, 2003), knowledge audit (Chong, 2004), knowledge management (Armstrong, 2006) knowledge management a case of Kenya (Mosoti and Masheka, 2010) knowledge creation (Ceptureanu and Captureanu, 2010) knowledge management practices (Mavodza and Ngulube 2011; Kafchehi, Taherkhoyani, Hasani, Sheikhesmaeili and Abdi, 2013; Gholami, Nazari, Nazari-Shirkouhi, Noruzy, 2013). Although these contributions by researchers have led to progress of knowledge based view, there is still difficulty in the part of employees and managers in organizations to see a clear link between their investments in knowledge implementation and the value the organization gets in terms of performance.

In Kenya, this is further compounded by a myriad of challenges facing TVET institutions. The successive governments have had challenges in funding technical institutions and also the society views technical education more as an alternative placement for students who could not make it in the formalized education system (Elkins, 2011). Poor allocation of resources to these institutions and takeovers of technical institutions by public universities under the watch of the government as has impacted negatively on technical education. The consequence of this is that the economy, the emerging and incumbent workers suffer (Elkins,

2011). Although the current government in Kenya has emphasized the role of TVET in developing the required human resource capacities, more emphasis has been put on infrastructure within TVET and little attention has been paid on employees in the institutions. This paper, therefore, explores and attempts to fill in the gap that exists in literature by analyzing the extent of relationships between knowledge implementation, employee engagement and employee performance in TVET institutions in Kenya.

Literature Review and Hypothesis

Development

Knowledge Implementation and Employee Performance

Broadly, the concept of employee performance has been examined from various perspectives namely; Resource Based View (Barney, 1991; Peteraf, 1993; Mahoney, 2005; Raduan, 2009) knowledge based view (Barney, 1991; Grant, 1996) and Balanced score card perspective (Kaplan, 1996:2012; Niven, 2002). According to Campbell *et al.*, (1990) and Viswesvaran *et al.*, (1996) employee performance are behaviors which employees display and are observable, measurable and valued by the organization because of its relevance to overall organizational goals. However, according to Schmidt (1996) and Viswesvaran and Ones (2000) individual employee performance has been a central variable in much research in relation to overall organization performance but as a construct, it has received little attention when compared with other relevant variables. This study therefore considered employee performance as dependent variable based on this gap in literature.

The study acknowledged the diversity of views from previous studies on the concept of employee performance and synthesized the components of Campbell *et al.*, (1996), Viswesvaran *et al.*, (1996) and Hakala (2008) and adopts the components that were viewed to be within the control of the employee and are measurable. These include; task proficiency competence or job knowledge, demonstration of effort, interpersonal competence, communication competence, leadership, maintenance of personal discipline, facilitation of peer and team performance, creativity and

adherence to policy.

Human capital theory (Coleman, 1998; Weisingera and Black, 2006; Styhre, 2008) concurs with resource based view (Barney, 1984; Teece *et al.*, 1997) that people add value to the organization through their knowledge, skills, experiences, talents and intelligent quotient. Ehrenberg and Smith (1994) further postulates that the knowledge and skills an employee has acquired through education, training and experience generates a stock of productive capital which emphasizes the added value that employees contribute to organizations. This value is further enhanced by encouraging knowledge implementation as a practice by employees and organisations. Employees can implement acquired knowledge to explore problems and create solutions and producing a structure for enhancing efficiency and effectiveness. Gholami *et al.*, (2013) notes that in the modern dynamic and complex environment, organizations need to acquire, create, share, save and implement new knowledge in order to make strategic decisions that can lead to improvements in productivity, financial and employee performance. This view is further supported by Teece *et al.*, (1997) who postulated that the ability of the organization to create, acquire, integrate and implement knowledge through employees has emerged as a critical component in enhancing performance.

Knowledge implementation means the application and use of both tacit and documented knowledge in decision-making and performance of tasks thus improving performance and achieving goals. Lin (2011), Gholami *et al.*, (2013) and Kafchehi *et al.*, (2013) concur that organizational knowledge should be implemented by employees in services, processes and products of the organization. Reich (1991) shares the same view and acknowledges that skills, knowledge and competences possessed and implemented by employees are key factors in determining whether organizations and nations will prosper. In the light of the above discussion the first hypothesis was formulated.

Ho1 There is a significant relationship between knowledge implementation and employee performance.

Employee Engagement and Employee

Performance

Employee engagement was first used by Khan in 1990 in his study "Psychological conditions of personal engagement and disengagement at work" which was published in the Academy of Management Journal. However, it was until the mid-1990s when Gallup started to refine and extend employee engagement by developing twelve items (Q12) to measure employee engagement which were then adopted and validated by many researchers through studies as well as practical considerations regarding its usefulness in the workplace (Harter and Creglow, 1998; Harter and Schmidt, 2000; Harter, Schmidt, and Hayes, 2002).

According to Khan (1990); Gallup (1995); Saks (2005:2006); Vance, (2006) and Hewitt (2012) an engaged employee is aware of the business context, consistently speak positively about the organization to co-workers and employees, have intense desire to be part of the organization, exert extra effort and engage in behavior that contributes to organizational success. However, this view was sharply contrasted by Murphy (2013) and Liaci Juapi (2014) in their empirical studies. Murphy (2013) in his study which linked employee engagement scores and employee appraisal scores established that workers who were deemed to be low performers in their annual review scored higher than those employees who were viewed as high performers. He further established that highly engaged employees were low performers and those employees who were low in engagement were high performers. The negative correlation between employee engagement and performance was further established by Jaupi and Llaci, (2014) in their study 'Employee Engagement and its Relation with Key Economic Indicators'. Jaupi and Llaci established that in Albania, the region that reported the lowest income per capita (GDP 24%), had the most employees engaged (76.4%). This further validates the argument that highly engaged employee are low performers. This implies that more research is needed to explore this new dimension and to build consensus.

Basing on the perspectives by Khan (1990), Gubman (2004), Baumruk (2004), Shaffer (2004), Murphy (2013) and Jaupi and Llaci (2014) the study notes that cognitive, emotional, behavioral or intellectual commitment by employees does

not guarantee improved performance. It is therefore, evident from extant literature that there is no agreed relationship between employee engagement and employee performance and this led to the second hypothesis.

H₀₂ Employee engagement moderates the relationship between knowledge implementation and employee performance.

Material and Methods

The study adopted explanatory research design to show the causal relationship between knowledge implementation, employee engagement and employee performance. The study used cluster sampling to arrive at the most representative region in Kenya in terms of types and number of technical institutions. The target population was 3147 employees in public technical institutions in Rift valley and 343 formed the sample size as per Cochran's formula. Random sampling technique was used to identify the respondents who filled the questionnaires. However, out of 343 respondents, 326 responded, hence giving a response rate of 95.04%. All items in the study were anchored on a five point likert scale. Questionnaires were validated through pretest and a panel of experts. Cronbach alpha tests were used to assess the reliability of the instrument and the computed Cronbach alpha coefficient results were all above 0.7 and this fall within the accepted limit by (Hair *et al.*, 2006).

Data were screened to assess whether the assumptions of regression were met. Normality of the distribution of data was tested graphically by inspection of histogram and p-p plots and numerically by Shapiro-Wilk test and the

findings were within the accepted thresholds of .05 and above. Linearity of study variables was tested using Pearson moment correlation and the inspection of the correlation matrix revealed that there is a linear relationship between the study variables. Independence of errors was checked using Durbin-Watson statistic and it was within the accepted threshold of 1.5 to 2.5 according to Hayes (2013). Multicollinearity was tested by running the Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) and the tolerance levels and standard cut-off points suggested by Scott (2003) were observed. Centering of variables was also done to counter multicollinearity as argued by (Aiken and West, 1991).

The tests for interaction were conducted in the study to establish the nature of moderation, and the extent to which employee engagement influences the association between knowledge implementation and employee performance. The test for moderation was performed using regression models following the steps by Baron and Kenny (1986). In probing further the nature of interaction, scatter plots were generated following Aiken and West (1991) and Hayes (2013) approach.

Results

Demographic Information of the Respondents

Demographic information hypothesized as age level of education and experience were used by the study as control variables in order to control for the possibility of variance. Control variables are viewed as important in the study as it lays ground for comparing performance among employees as argued by Armstrong (2006), Basu and Sengupta (2007) and Bashir, Liaojianqiao, Ghazanfar and Mahroof (2011).

Table 1: Demographic Information of the Respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentages
Gender		
Male	150	47%
Female	169	53%
Age		
18-25 years	24	7.5%
26-33 years	97	30.4%
34-41 years	128	40.1%
42-48 years	61	19.1%
49-55 years	9	2.8%
Level of education		
Diploma	64	20.1%
Higher diploma	64	20.1%
Degree	109	34.2%
Masters	70	21.9%
PhDs	12	3.8%
Number of years work		
0-5 years	104	32.6%
6-10 years	95	29.8%
11-15 years	63	19.7%
16-20 years	37	11.6%
21-25 years	13	4.1%
26 Above	7	2.2%

Source: Survey Data, (2015)

Testing Moderation

Moderation tests were performed to following the steps by Baron and Kenny (1986) and using hierarchical multiple regressions were used. Control variables were first entered into the

model (model 1), followed by the main effects (model 2) and finally the interaction terms were entered (model 3). The results are summarized in Table 2 and 3.

Table 2: Regression Models

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 2	Model 3
Constant (employee performance)	1.880(.029)	1.880(.029)	1.879(.028)	1.879(.027)
Z score Age	.0101(.029)*	.099(.042)***	.085(.041)*	.089(.040)*
Z score level of education	-.087(.034)*	-.081(.034)**	-.090(.033)*	-.090(.032)*
Z score number of years worked with current employer	-.113(.039)**	-.105(.039)*	-.081(.038)*	-.076(.037)**
Z score Knowledge implementation		.083(.029)**	.015(.031)	-.53(.033)
Z score employee engagement			.155(.031)**	.174(.031)**
Zscore interaction terms (knowledge implementation and employee engagement)				-.142(.030)**
R ²	.049	.073	.141	.199
Adjusted R ²	.040	.061	.127	.183
R ² change	.049	.024	.092	.058
F statistic	5.321	6.093	16.600	22.189
Durbin- Watson	1.684	1.729	1.835	1.986

*P<.1**P<.05***P<.01

Values of unstandardized beta coefficients, with standard error in parenthesis

Source: Survey Data, (2015)

From model 1, the results indicates that control variables, age ($\beta=.101$, $p<.05$) and level of education ($\beta=-.087$, $p<.05$) and experience ($\beta=-.113$, $p<.05$) had a statistically significant effect on employee. The R^2 value of 0.049 implies that the control variables contributes 4.9% of the variance in employee performance and this is statistically significant as shown by the F change statistic (5.321, $p<.01$). The model fit is indicated by the coefficient of determination R^2 with a value of .049 and adjusted R^2 with a value of .040.

Model 2 indicates that the entry of the predictor variable conceptualized as knowledge implementation increased the model predictive capacity to 7.3% as shown by R^2 with a value of .073. This implies that knowledge implementation explains 2.4% of variation in employee performance after age, level of education and number of years worked have been controlled as shown by R^2 change with a value of .024. Therefore there is a significant relationship between knowledge implementation and employee performance ($\beta=.083$, $p<.05$) and thus first hypothesis (H01) was accepted. The overall predictive capacity of the model in explaining the variation in employee performance is 7.3 % and this is statistically significant as shown by F change statistic in Table 3 (6.093, $p<.01$). The findings further indicate a goodness of fit as shown by the coefficient of determination R^2 with a value of .073 and adjusted R^2 value of .061.

Model 3 shows that the entry of the moderator

variable conceptualized as employee engagement increased the model predictive capacity to 14.1% as shown by R^2 with a value of .141. This implies that employee engagement explains .6.8% of variation in employee performance as shown by R^2 change with a value of .068. Employee engagement is a significant predictor of employee performance ($\beta=.155$, $p<.01$). The overall model is significant in predicting employee performance as shown by the corresponding F change statistic in the Table 3 (10.153, $P<.01$). The findings further indicate a goodness of fit as shown by the coefficient of determination R^2 with a value of .141 and adjusted R^2 value of .127.

In model 4, the entry of interaction terms resulted in R^2 change of .058. This implies that the interaction between knowledge implementation and employee engagement increased the model's predictive capacity in explaining the variation in employee performance by 5.8 % to a total of 19.9%. The increase is statistically significant as shown by the F change statistic (22.189, $p<.01$). The overall model is also significant as indicated by F change statistic in Table 3 (12.739, $p<.01$). The findings further revealed a goodness of fit as indicated by the coefficient of determination R^2 with a value of .199 and the adjusted R^2 value of .183. Moderation therefore occurred as indicated by the significance of R^2 change and the significant effect by the interaction terms ($\beta=-.142$ $p<.01$).

Table 3: Anova Output

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	14.847	3	4.949	5.321	.001 ^b
	Residual	289.239	311	.930		
	Total	304.086	314			
2	Regression	42.908	5	8.582	10.153	.000 ^c
	Residual	261.177	309	.845		
	Total	304.086	314			
3	Regression	60.460	6	10.077	12.739	.000 ^d
	Residual	243.626	308	.791		
	Total	304.086	314			

The results in Table 1 revealed that the interaction between knowledge implementation and employee engagement is statistically significant ($\beta = -.142$, $p < .01$). This leads to the acceptance of hypothesis two. The findings confirmed that employee engagement significantly moderates the relationship between knowledge implementation and employee performance though negatively. The negative correlation implies that as engagement levels increase, employee performance decreases. To further explore the nature of interaction in hypothesis two, scatter plots were generated where employee performance was regressed onto knowledge

implementation across two and three levels of engagement as shown by the different colors used in generating the scatter plots. The levels of engagement were conceptualized by the study as low engagement and depicted by blue scatter plots, moderate engagement depicted by brown scatter plots and high engagement depicted by green scatter plots. Interactions were plotted by adding fit lines to the groups to facilitate interpretation as posited by Hayes (2013). Figure 1 shows knowledge implementation and employee performance depicted on two levels of engagement namely low engagement and high engagement.

Figure 1 Scatter Plots on Knowledge Implementation, and Employee Performance on Two Levels of Engagement

Source: Survey data, (2015)

The findings in Figure 1 illustrates that low engaged employees are high performers in knowledge implementation as shown by (R^2 linear=0.126) while highly engaged employees are low performers in knowledge implementation as indicated by (R^2 linear=0.009). To further ascertain if low

engaged employees are high performers, the study categorized employee engagement into three levels namely low, moderate and high. Scatter plots were generated illustrating knowledge implementation and employee performance depicted on three levels of employee engagement as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2 Scatter Plots on Knowledge Implementation, and Employee Performance on Three Levels of Engagement

Source: Survey Data, (2015)

The findings in Figure 2 revealed a consistent trend where low engaged employees performed highly in knowledge implementation as shown by (R^2 linear=0.115), followed by moderately engaged employees shown by (R^2 linear=0.003). Those who performed dismally in knowledge implementation were employees who were highly engaged as illustrated by (R^2 linear=1.60E-4) which is a smaller value. It is evident from both levels of engagement that, there is a clear and consistent trend where employees who deliver value to the organization are low in engagement followed by employees who are moderately engaged and those who are highly engaged are poor performers.

Discussion of Findings

Demographic Information

The findings indicated a positive relationship ($\beta=.101$ $p<.05$) between age and employee performance implying that as age increases employees improve in terms of performance because they gain experience as years go by and this in turn improves their performance. Further, level of education and employee performance was found to be negatively related ($\beta=-.087$ $p<.05$). This implies that the higher the level of education the poorer the performance and this can be attributed to the training policy by

the employer which does not recognize masters and doctorate degrees in terms of pay. Furthermore, the policy is discriminatory in the sense that teachers are granted study leave with or without pay depending on the teaching subjects and level of education to be pursued. For instance, study leave policy does not grant study leave with pay to teachers in TVET who wish to pursue doctoral degrees. Teachers in their quest to advance their careers through further studies are forced to enroll for further studies without the knowledge of the employer. In addition, the non-teaching staffs in TVET are employed by board of management. The study established through literature that training and development policies vary from institution to institution and most institutions do not have funds for employee training and development (Ministry of Education Science and Technology, 2011). This limits employees in acquiring new knowledge through various programs.

Results showed a negative relationship between the number of years an employee has worked with the current employer and employee performance ($\beta=-.113$ $p<.05$). This implies that the more an employee stays in an organization the less productive they become (Bashir et al., 2011). This could be attributed to employees being too comfortable with their non-performance and more so where there are no clear set targets on knowledge implemented

which make employees to lag behind in accountability.

Knowledge Implementation and Employee Performance

The study tested the first hypothesis that stated that there is a statistically significant relationship between knowledge implementation and employee performance and the results confirmed that there is a significant relationship ($\beta=.083$ $p<.05$). Therefore the hypothesis was accepted. The influence of knowledge implementation on employee performance in technical institutions could be attributed to top management support in employee learning, sharing of knowledge and using of acquired knowledge in making decisions related to work. This encourages employees to be creative and innovative and thus improved performance as argued by Captureanu and Captureanu (2010) and Gholami *et al.*, (2013). The significant relationship can be further attributed to a supportive culture that enhances knowledge implementation and top management support through allocation of monetary and non-monetary resources to facilitate knowledge implementation as revealed by the study findings.

The Moderating Effect of Employee Engagement on the Relationship between Knowledge

Implementation and Employee Performance

The second hypothesis tested in the study was that employee engagement moderates the relationship between knowledge implementation and employee performance. The study results confirmed that employee engagement significantly moderates the relationship between knowledge implementation and employee performance ($\beta=-.142$ $p<.01$). Therefore the hypothesis was accepted. The introduction of the moderator changed the nature and the strength of the relationship from positive and significant to negative and significant. This implies that employee engagement negatively moderates the relationship between knowledge implementation and employee performance. This implies that as employee engagement increases, employee performance decreases. The

study findings concurs with literature (Murphy 2013; Jaupi and Llaci 2014) that highly engaged employees are low performers while low engaged employees are high performers.

Loehr (2005) stresses that becoming fully engaged at work, is the pathway for igniting talents, skills and for making a real difference in performance. However the results of the study state the contrary. The study therefore argues that because employees who are fully engaged are positive, energetic, dedicated, and resilient, they can be easily noticed by managers and are less likely to be held accountable for poor performance, terminated or laid off thus giving them advantage over low engaged employees who are high performers. This is also a pointer that low performers in knowledge implementation may not be aware that they are performing dismally and may not be corrected at all. Murphy (2013) posits that low performers who are highly engaged often end up with the easiest jobs because managers do not ask much of them and that high performers who are low in engagement stay late in the offices correcting the mistakes of poor performers which creates a feeling of frustration and unfairness. To further support this perspective, a study by Leadership IQ, (2015) that covered more than 70000 respondents established that 87% of the respondents said that working with low performers made them want to change their jobs and 93% agreed to the fact that working with low performers decreased their productivity. Top performers are always stressed up because they are often counted on by the boss who regularly assigns them work though they are undervalued and not recognized by the same bosses. Another pointer why highly engaged employees are performing poorly could be attributed to the fact that their rational commitment, emotional commitment and intention to stay in the organization could be motivated by other factors like prospects in career progress, promotions, or prestige other than performance. This therefore implies that for TVET institutions to achieve the benefits of knowledge implementation, managers should firmly and frankly speak with high, middle and low performers concerning their results and the consequences of their performance. Furthermore, there is need for TVET managers

to clearly differentiate between employee engagement and employee performance and reward appropriately to avoid workers hiding their poor performance in their high engagement scores.

The finding of the study is further supported by Jaupi and Llaci, (2014) who established a negative correlation between employee engagement and performance in their study 'Employee Engagement and its Relation with Key Economic Indicators'. The study established that in Albania, the region that reported the lowest income per capita (GDP 24%), had the most employees engaged (76.4%). This therefore, further validates the argument that highly engaged employees in are low performers.

Conclusions

Knowledge implementation has a significant effect on employee performance in TVET institutions in Kenya. The study builds on resource-based view, knowledge-based view, and human capital theory and submits that knowledge as a strategic resource can be utilized by organization to gain advantage in performance. People add value to the organization through their knowledge, skills, experiences, talents and intelligent quotient which cannot be imitated or substituted by competitor's particularly tacit knowledge and social capital which exists in the relationships among persons and enables employees to mutually share and implement knowledge in tackling tasks and solving work related problems which in turn facilitates employee performance.

The moderator hypothesized as employee engagement significantly and negatively moderated the relationship between knowledge implementation and employee performance. This indicates that highly engaged employees are low performers in knowledge implementation while high performers are low in engagement. This should be a cause of concern and a wakeup call for TVET managers and administrators who for a long time believed that highly engaged employees are high performers in all area. In a nutshell, the study has empirically established that employee engagement is a true moderator in the relationship between knowledge

implementation and employee performance in technical institution in Kenya.

Theoretical and Managerial Implications

Contributions of Findings to Theory

According to extant literature it has been acknowledged that more efforts are needed to extend the resource based view, knowledge based view and human capital theory from merely examining the resource attributes to analyzing the extent of the relationship between these resources and other related variables towards achieving improved performance (Schuller, 2000; Peteraf *et al.*, 2003 and Rodriguez, 2005). To this end, this study has contributed to filling this gap by empirically studying the relationship between knowledge implementation and employee performance and by assessing the role the moderator in the relationship between knowledge implementation and employee performance.

Managerial Implications

Knowledge as a resource is an intangible asset which should have measures of performance like other resources` in the organization. Objectives, indicators and measures of performance should be integrated into the management systems of TVET institutions and should be reflected in evaluation of employee performance. The study further recommends that for TVET institutions to achieve the benefits of knowledge implementation, managers should firmly and frankly speak with high, middle and low performers concerning their results and the consequences of their performance. This will enhance accountability and reward of high performers, while middle and low performers can be encouraged to improve. This will further help the institutions to identify employee training needs in knowledge implementation, employee engagement and performance and design appropriate training programs. This can be achieved if managers differentiate between engagement scores and performance scores.

The study therefore, provides a basis to policy makers for making policy guidelines and interventions on knowledge implementation and employee engagement in order to improve employee performance in technical institutions.

Recommendations for Future Research

The results of this study have shown a remarkable leading factor in assessing the contribution of knowledge implementation, employee engagement and employee performance. However, this study was confined on knowledge implementation, employee engagement and employee performance in

TVET institutions in rift valley Kenya hence limiting the generalizability of the findings. To augment the research findings of this study, the study recommends a replica study to explore these findings in other countries in Africa and other part of the world. This will improve the generalizability of findings.

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APPENDIX1: QUESTIONNAIRE

PART I: KNOWLEDGE IMPLEMENTATION

Using the response scale below, kindly tick beside the statement that best expresses your opinion on implementation

	Knowledge implementation	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	I use the knowledge i acquire in making decisions related to my work					
2	My organizations top management supports me to learn					
3	My organizations top management supports me to share knowledge					
4	My organizational top management supports me to use acquired knowledge in delivering my duties					
5	My organizational culture supports me to learn					
6	My organizational culture supports me to share knowledge					
7	My organizational culture supports me to use of knowledge					
8	My organization has a dedicated monetary resources for knowledge implementation					
9	My organization has a dedicated non-monetary resources for knowledge implementation					

PART II: EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT

Please indicate whether you agree with the following statements

		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
1	Iam proud of my employer					
2	Iam Satisfied with my employer					
3	Iam satisfied with my Job					
4	I have an opportunity to perform well at challenging work					

5	I get recognition and positive feedback for my contributions to the institution					
6	I have personal support from my supervisor					
7	I put effort above and beyond the minimum required					
8	I understand the link between my job and the organization's mission					
9	I have Prospects for future growth with my employer					
10	I have the intention to stay with my employer					
11	We work as a team to improve the performance the of institutional					
12	I know exactly what I need to do to contribute to my team's performance					
13	I balance between my work and personal commitments and this is right for me.					

PART II: DEMOGRAPHICS AND OTHER IMPORTANT INFORMATION

Please tick the box that describes you

1) Age

18-25 years 26-33 years 34-41 years 42-48 years 49-55 years

2) Gender Male female

3) Highest level of education attained

Diploma Higher Diploma Degree Masters PhD

4) Number of years you have worked with your current employer.

0-5 6-10 11-15 16-20 21-25 Above 25